

The Management of the Urban Project between Challenge and Need: The Case of the Modernization Project of Constantine

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Abstract—In this article, and through the modernization project of metropolis of Constantine (PMMC) experience in Algeria, discussed to highlight the importance of management in an urban project at various levels: strategic and operational.

The statement we attended to reach is to evaluate the modernization project of metropolis of Constantine in the light of management and prove the relation between a good urban management and the success of an urban project.

Keywords—Urban project, strategic management, operational management, the modernization project of Constantine.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE cities of today are no longer what they were, they develop quickly and face the increasingly difficult challenges to raise, between sustainability, rapid urbanization, and multiplication of actors, they become difficult to manage.

The urban project is the alternative to an urban planning which has demonstrated its weaknesses and which has lifted the curtain on its many failures, he is in some way the hope of cities to become sustainable, to master their urbanization and put the actors on the same objectives. However, being a few controlled practice, the urban project has need to be reframed, conducted and monitored, given that it appeals to a multiplicity of actors, to the management of a space and a time of influence, which may exceed its perimeter and even its process, and even more to governance, which can assume its greatness. A challenge is then launched; the management, which is a practice of the world of the business and the enterprise, finds an echo in the urban to meet this challenge by using practices in the world of business and transposes them onto the urban project while trying to adapt to the realities and the complexity of the urban phenomenon [1], [2], [3].

The management of the urban project is located between the challenge of providing assistance and some resolution to this complexity and the need to act for a better result and good urban product [4], [5]. Besides this, it stimulates innovation in the context of introducing new urban practices through methods and tools aimed to manage, organize, plan, decide and control the complex process of the project urban.

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Through this article, the failures of an operation which implementation has remained outside of the practices of management, call into question the practices of the current urban project.

From the macro to the micro scale, speaking management does necessarily refer to the world of business and organizations, since that is its origin; so it will be to present this practice in his originating world and then move to the urban one. However it would be appropriate to remind the new practice of urban planning, it is a matter of managing, namely the "urban project".

Finally, an example of failure of the operation of urban improvement, part of the urban project for the modernization of Constantine "PMMC" will shed light on the need for strategic management of the urban project and operational management of the performing of various operations and actions of its program.

II. ABOUT URBAN PROJECT

If well make the city is to adapt it to the needs and the expectations of those who live in, the question, which rises is how so? Moreover, if urban planning is all actions that may be undertaken to make the city, the planning remains the answer to How to fabricate the city. This 'How has been tackled by several approaches, coupled with the changes that the world has known either side of the economic, social and transformation of society, or of the environment and its safety, gave birth to the process of planning interventions on the urban fabric. This planning becoming strategic, is a new approach which wants to be of quality and not of quantity, which takes into account the needs and expectations of the residents and which is more listening to them, which intervenes take into account the context by being closer more of the concrete reality, bringing together the multitude of skills for improved making of the city and especially who arrives to juggle between long and short-term and also between public and private interests.

Taking into account of the inhabitant and of the changing society, the environment, of environmental concerns and the economy, which is never stable, led to the balance of the sustainable development spheres and this planning is based on the principles of sustainable urban development. However, implement the strategic planning at the urban scale needs transformation in the organization of studies, in decision-making, as well as in the procedure. «The neo-urbanism is an approach particularly ambitious, which requires more

knowledge, more experience and more democracy"[6]. The use of this planning has highlighted the desire to renew the urbanism by passing from an urbanism of plan to the urbanism of project; and in this strategic planning; the urban project occupies a central place [7].

"Any intervention on the city today is qualified by urban project" [8]; the concept of the urban project is very frequent in several speeches. Those of politicians in trying to win the trust of voters, those of professionals in trying to legitimize and to appoint the actions they produce and the designs of which they are the fathers. It is almost commonly admitted that the idea of the urban project comes from a critic of the urban planning regulatory and technocratic planning. However, if the urban project is a criticism of the functional urban planning that is more concerned about the respect of rules than the city itself as a space of social practices, is it good enough just to adjust these rules? Is it just needed more of competences for the design and the implementation of urban actions? A multidisciplinary and reconciliation of all the sciences will it be the adequate response? Is it necessary to protect ourselves and see the facts on the long term or better focus on localism and the present moment? Finally, is revolutionizing all the most necessary: methods, visions, planning, prospecting and approaches to improve the fabric of the city?

The revolution is engaged by the urban project, it targets the city by using a new approach, that of the "project" and not the plan. This approach of *projicio* (bearing in itself the notion of the future by its meaning) is intended to combine a strategic vision and specific actions, it is impregnated the local context and acts on the whole of the city.

The urban project combines economy and society in the context of an intervention on the space and joins the current sustainable development where the city is an ecosystem, an all seated and in which the components interact. It is the product of a political choice and benefited from its portage, yet does not exclude the private sector initiative and the imperative of the participation of users and residents of the city.

III. MANAGE A COMPANY, MANAGE A CITY: THE TRANSPOSITION

It is with the advent of the urban project that the metaphor of the city such as industrial company[9] becomes more meaningful; This metaphor can be explained and justified by the role of the city in the economy that has been highlighted during the triggering of the revolution of the urban project by characterizing the city of big business that brings together several enterprises, created of the employs and maintains an economic dynamic.

Some mayors say they manage their city as a company; for urban projects, it is the methods of management, process and approach that are transposed. This is the case of the Euralille project, which is inspired by the approach the management of the enterprise as asserts J. P. Baietto, a main actor of the project during an interview in 1995, by saying: "a strategic approach, from engineering methods of business, has given

the guiding principles for the management and implementation of the project "[10]. Thus, management interfered in urban planning and more precisely in the urban project to facilitate its implementation and to better understand its complexity. It has even become a necessity. In fact, the emergence of the urban project itself implies the necessity of the project management of the fact of multiple mutations that he has brought with him, namely, the new modes of doing, the actors and their multiplication, the marketing and the work on the image of the city, the land tenure and financial montage with the partnership and participation which is at the heart of the project. Therefore «... the conceptual approaches cannot be separated from the issue of the management of urban projects, even if this area requires specific knowledge"[1] this is justified by the characteristic of the urban project which among other requires the management as the expressed AVITABLE A in saying that the urban project is "a strategic approach oriented toward a work of management within a system of sets of actors with a device of pilotage " [1]. Yes, the management of the urban project is essential for the success of that one; but also for the operational implementation, and yes, also, it requires new knowledge very specific to the urban, since even if the city can be managed as a company, this does not exclude the particularities and the complexity it has in relation to it.

IV. MANAGE A SUSTAINABLE URBAN PROJECT

The concept of the management of urban project has emerged in recent years in such a way as inevitable given the changes and upheaval of organizations and occupations. He introduced this key link between the various phases of the urban project in order to restrict the segmentation and optimize the implementation; the conditions for the emergence of urban project are supported by the awareness that the action on the city is complex and requires a collective work to achieve the effectiveness; but more importantly, put in before the consensus rather than the decision and the intent rather than the drawing.

In the urban project, it is no longer a question only of management of projects, but the urban strategic management, this dimension of the management is generally perceived as being the construction of acceptable strategies, achievable and reversible [6] that may base an urban planning and layout, reflective and contributing [6].

If we pierce the mystery of urban strategic management, we will be faced with prospecting principles "the strategic aspect" of participation "the aspect of acceptability", detailed feasibility studies and opportunity "aspect of reliability "but also iterativity and flexibility of action," the reversibility aspect while pushing reflection and association of more actors possible for a co-production," the aspect of reflexivity. "

The management of project introduced in the urban project or in the management of the city created new forms of cooperation with the aspects that we have just quote but also thanks to the aspect of the management and leadership. The management is also the management of the project through the

looking vision, strategic and more specifically the planning, piloting, monitoring and control of the project.

The urban project is of a complex nature, it cannot follow a process and a process flow well determined. However, some phases are common to all urban projects, we have illustrated this process (Fig. 1) in order to be able to exploit and detecting the intervention of the management, its integration, its levels and the integration of its fields.

Fig. 1 Process of the urban project and levels of management A: The urban project is both the production process and the final product.

B: the process of the urban project is iterative. C: the project initiation may be due to a political ambition followed by a portage, a crisis of the city, the needs expressed by the civil society or a detection of a development opportunity. D: the planning must be reactivated and leaves opportunities for adjustments (after negotiation, consultation, elements of major force, etc.). E: The process should be interactive with the participation of all the actors and with coordination.

Through this schematization, we can clearly distinguish three levels of management: strategic, tactical and operational. These levels are actually the prioritization of tasks to be accomplished to ensure the smooth running of the project, as will the extent and of broad guidelines to the details.

A. The Strategic Urban Management

The strategic management is the definition of main lines, guidelines and the setting of objectives and the means to achieve them, it allows you to control the urban result and define the product. It can be defined as "the strategic deliberation and the formulation of choice" [11], it is also responsible for organizing the instances and the actors in order to best organize and find the structure the more adapted to the project.

The strategic management refers to the long term and to the combination of internal and external elements and to the overall vision, it is for this reason that it is associated with the strategic decision.

Usually, in the businesses, it is at the level of the general direction that the strategy is fixed or the strategic management

is carried out, this is in the cases where the method of management exercised is the management policy. In the urban, it is at the level of public authorities, elected officials and in the administrations that this management is carried out.

The strategic management, whether that be in a policy method or participatory, must meet the actors of the project (stakeholders) to avoid the conflict and build consensus.

The strategic management follows a phasing in iterative process (Fig. 2), starting with the analysis of the situation and of the current state for the detection of needs and the identification of opportunities, then the thorough reflection on the challenges and the solutions finally, the decision and the strategic choice.

Fig. 2 Process of strategic management

The strategic management should, thus, be at the upstream of the urban project, it might be in itself the triggering of the urban project with a level of detail low on the actions.

The main bases of this management are: the strategic diagnosis, the strategic choice and the strategic deployment of resources [11].

B. The Tactical Management

Translation phase from political ambitions and strategic orientations to the action plans and in concrete actions, this is where the tactical management is.

It is essentially the answer to questions related to how and when, as well, the extended is reduced since the projects are targeted and formalized and the level of detail increases. In the case of Large Urban Projects, the tactic management is the management to define and formalize the projects and operations constituting the major urban project.

At this stage, several elements will be identified: the actors, the resources, timelines, key milestones, the envelopes allocated etc., but it is to be noted that one of the major roles of the tactic management is to ensure and verify the consistency between the strategy and the translations into actions in order to follow a logical flow between the scope and the details.

The tactical management works in both directions. It means that it not only reflects the strategic guidelines in action plans but also decodes the realities from the operational management for the strategy to be called in question or completed. As well, the tactic management is the interface between the top of the pyramid (the scope) and its base (the

details).

C. The Operational Management

Operational management is action planning being shared between tactical and operational project level (real time). Then, we talk about management of deadlines, risk management, monitoring of operations, communication management and costs management, while ensuring the quality of implementation, organizing and leading production teams.

The operational management is the extension and the completion of the strategic management through the implementation of the strategic management decisions translated into plans of action by the tactical management.

It is to manage in real time the specific actions that must be undertaken in order to achieve the action, tactic plans and strategic orientations. The level of detail is thus very important and related to the targeted actions in content, time of realization, costs, teams...

D. The Articulation between the Levels of Management

The levels of management are (must be) complementary, as it is to create consistency and none of the confusion. Thus, the operational management is part of implementation of action plans defined by the tactical management and which fall within the guidelines of strategic management. However, it should also be noted that strategic management can be influenced by operational management (iterative circle), since it must take into account the information provided by ascending field realities and decoded by the tactical management; So strategic management is based on the operational management for detecting the inconsistencies and weaknesses failure of the strategy itself.

The tactical management plays a very important role in this joint, it allows the consistency of the strategy in relation to on field activities, as it ensures the transmission top-down but also bottom-up information (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3 Interaction and complementarity between the levels of management

The creation of an iterative cycle allowing this transmission is essential so that the strategy and actions are flexible and that all decisions can be reversible, since management tends to master this irreversibility and promote flexibility although

uncertainty is characteristic of the urban project.

The articulation between these two dimensions of management is often difficult. Indeed, the more the project is large, the more complex it becomes to bring the strategy to the field; thus, the multiplication of actors is the major factor of difficulty of this articulation and the actors' management and the management of the communication are the solution.

E. Management of Actors:

The actors also have their weight in the management both strategic and operational in the urban project. To this effect, the schema of organization of actors and of implementation of the urban project is inspired by the project management in the businesses based on the model of the concurrent engineering. This new organization is opposed to the sequencing of the project and to the hierarchical separation of actors.

F. The Management of the Communication

Since the urban project involves a variety of actors, the communication and the passage of information between them is a crucial point. The purpose of the communication management is to facilitate and enable this good communication. The management of communication is a success factor of the overall management of the project,

It is responsible of generate, distribute, report, and the storage of information which must be sufficient in quality and quantity corresponding each actor of the project. In this way, the sharing and the control of information is ensured with a dictionary providing in turn a repository and a common vocabulary.

The bad management of communication in the project may have irreversible impacts on the quality, the period for achievement and of course the cost of the project. In most cases, these problems are due to the non-identification upstream of any chain of cast member, several researchers have highlighted the importance of not forgetting no link (actor) in this string [1], [12]. In effect the emergence of a new cast member in mid-path is often synonymous with conflict, then the management of communication must take charge of this imperative well upstream of the process of the project. Most often, this forgotten actor is the citizen, after the implementation of the process of realization, he claimed to be informed, he is opposed to certain conditions or project in itself and this has an impact on the time frame for achievement, on the pre-set plan and even on the contents of the project, this refers to the need to involve the citizen upstream of the project. Therefore, "The active participation of citizens in the project is the most powerful instrument to reduce conflict in the construction phase"[12].

V. THE PROJECT FOR THE MODERNIZATION OF THE METROPOLIS OF CONSTANTINE (PMMC): THE FUTURE OF A METROPOLIS IN CRISIS

One of the most ancient cities not only in Algeria, but in the entire world, Constantine, the city of more than 20 centuries (2500 years ago) metropolis of the east of Algeria. Known as the most resistant city, it has faced several century of wars,

built on a very particular site of a singular rock, it is the city of bridges. However, for a city of this reputation, being characterized by the unsanitary conditions and lack of infrastructure undermines its image very much. Thus, today, Constantine is in a race against time, under the pressure of many constraints, it faces a challenge of its image evolution and improvement, since it is not only the city of beautiful landscapes, rocks, bridges and waterfalls of the Rhumel, it is also the city of the footprint, of the mass periurbanisation, of the urban saturation, of crisis of housing, crisis of equipment, lack of dynamic...

Urban planning in the city of Constantine wants to become a strategic planning wants to restore coherence to individual projects and the spontaneous and non-coherent development. A strong political conveyance and ambition of a wali who wants to mark his passage but also develop its city, generated the project of modernization of the city of Constantine PMMC. In fact, the PMMC as urban project falls into the category of major projects umbrellas sheltering in him several other projects that must be consistent in order to create a unified strategy. Its purpose is the creation of an urban dynamic for a sustainable development of Constantine and to evolve its image and acquire a statue of regional modern metropolis and why not international. Indeed, the objectives of the PMMC were shared between resolve the crisis and urban problems suffered (and still suffers from) the city and boost the whole of the metropolitan area for an external

attractiveness of the metropolis. However, its priority was to give coherence and articulation between the different projects said structuring of the city to allow a strategic planning that includes as main condition the comprehensive and coherent vision of development. Thus, an integrated vision that can bring together all the sectors around the same objectives and the same aiming, such is the ultimate goal of the PMMC, in other words to converge the respective interests of each sector on the same strategy and this for the realization of the great Constantine [13].

Having ambition for the modernization of the metropolis of Constantine, the objectives of the PMMC are located between solve the urban crisis and achieve the attractiveness and economic takeoff. They summarize the following points [13]:

- Revaluation of the image of Constantine;
- Modernization; by equipment;
- Improvement of living conditions and the comfort;
- Revitalization of development; (investment)
- Realization of social equity (cohesion and reduction of disparities);

The actions, operations and structuring projects (Fig. 4) entering in the program of the project for the modernization of Constantine are spread on the entire metropolitan area of Constantine, as showed in Fig. 4 [14] and on the time scale that reaches the year 2016 through short-term projects (1 to 3 years), medium (3 to 5 years) and long term (5 to 10 years).

Fig. 4 Geographic location of the projects in the city of Constantine [14]

VI. THE PROJECT FOR THE MODERNIZATION OF THE METROPOLIS OF CONSTANTINE: FAILURE OF STRATEGIC AND OPERATIONAL MANAGEMENT

To demonstrate the importance of the management in the

urban project, it must be remembered that the management begins with the strategic level then the operational level, which in the project for the Modernization of Constantine takes the pace of projects and small operations on field. Therefore, the project assessment from a managerial point of

view "strategic management" and then the evaluation of an operation "operational management" should enlighten us on the need of the management in the urban project in general.

A. Strategic Management

The project for the modernization of the metropolis of Constantine is a very ambitious project, however, the analysis of the strategy and its management revealed the following failures:

- The strategic vision has not taken into account the multi temporality of the project; in fact, the strategy based on a strong political conveyance but which has a schedule, with the end of the mandate of the Wali of Constantine "BOUDIAF". The project has become a sort of orphaned child once a new Wali has become;
- The strategic management, which should define the realistic and achievable actions within the period and in the context of available resources, has not been a success. Since the delays in implementation of the various action

plans made a myth of this realizability, and who says delays says additional cost;

- The actors were not the center of the project strategic management, in fact, between those who are set to the gap (the inhabitant in particular) and those involved lately (the various executive directions), the management of the actors has been lacking to the project;
- The aspect of flexibility and reversibility of the strategy also has not been studied in the strategic management of the project, actually, the actions and the strategy itself can no longer adapt to new data for urban management (change of Wali, events "Constantine the Capital of Arab Culture")

Finally, through the analysis and diagnosis of managerial strategy of the project, it becomes evident that a strategic management has not had the place that he should have and has not had the expected effect for such a big ambition.

TABLE I
THE ACTORS OF THE URBAN IMPROVEMENT OPERATION

Institution & status	Type of action	Partner
Ministry of Finance	Recovery of vacant property abandoned by the settlers	-Areas -Land Agency
Department of Housing and Town Planning	Promulgates laws and instruments of planning and development of the Territory	Wilaya
WILAYA (territorial public Community)	-Fixed the perimeter of rehabilitation action; -Designated the operator;	DAIRA&DLEP, OPGI; DUC; APC.
DAIRA	-Administrative Coordination	Wilaya
OPERATOR	-Intermediary designated by decision of the wali to manage the operation of rehabilitation -Urges the bureau to study -Engage the technical check of the CTC	Wilaya
BUREAU OF STUDIES	-Diagnosing buildings; -Develop the studies and propose solutions; -Assess the rehabilitation work and prepare the specifications for the consultation of enterprises -Monitor and control the work of rehabilitation	DUC; DLEP OPGI APC
DLEP	-Master of the Book of rehabilitation operations Equipment and Housing	OPGI; APC; BET; Company
APC (territorial collectivity of base Composed of Several Directorates and services)	-Facilities, gardens, public spaces, repair work VRD, sanitation, public lighting -Demolition, cleanup, waste management -Establishment of the technical sheet White program Algeria, TUP-EIIP	-Subdivisions Public Works, DLEP
Environment Directorate(OF)	Awareness and protection of the environment Waste Management and green spaces	APC
Society of water (SEACO-SEM)	Management of public services of drinking water and sanitation	APC; Duke
SECTOR (Arrondissement under the services of the APC)	Establishment of technical datasheets	APC; BET; Company
Office of Promotion and of Real Estate Management (OPGI)	Management and promotion of its park real estate	APC; DLEP; BET &Company
DUC	-Mastery of book of the urban Improvement -Establishment of technical datasheets for the authorization of the program; -Preparation of specifications of load for launch of the studies and monitoring of the project; -Collaborate with the master of the work for the launch of the realization of the work of the project.	Wilaya APC Services of local communities BET Company
Directorate of social action and solidarity (DAS)	Management of the Algeria white, distribution of the budget allocated to local communities	APC Sector

B. Operational Management

Moving from the strategic dimension to the operational one, scale will be reduced to an operation within the program of the Constantine modernization project, which will effectively demonstrate the importance of operational management.

The operations of urban improvement, spread over several areas of the city, are part of the components of the PMMC, a survey was made under a session of the APW (assemble populaire de la wilaya) of Constantine in which we take apart of the program [15]. These operations have shown deficiencies both in management, design, implementation and execution;

we will shed light on the basis of the investigations carried out in this direction.

There was a lack of urban mediation and concertation that would have led to successful citizen participation. Surveys, allowed us to see at the level of urban improvement enterprises operations, that the problems are related to two major causes: first, the confusion of roles and lack of stakeholders' coordination, and second, a lack of consultation

and citizen non-participation [15].

1. Organization of actors:

Table I gives an overview on the actors who are involved in the operations to improve urban and their roles [15].

The representation of these actors in their organizational scheme is as in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5 Organization of the actors in the operations of urban improvement

Through the analysis of these actors and their actual intervention on the field, the finding of the absence of coordination but also of cooperation is to denote, the inhabitant, which is a key actor, is located completely out of this process. This finding is summarized in the following points [15]:

- The relations between the actors are so anarchic and not as a network in order to be able to produce the good coordination;
- This organization is characterized by anarchy and a lack of coordination between bodies. also one of the most obvious point is the absence of the inhabitant as an actor;
- The division of administrative sectors is fragmented, and tasks distribution is compartmentalized;
- The disorganization of the involved actors, lack of coordination;

2. The Participation of Inhabitants:

Regarding the participation the survey has revealed the following points [15]:

- The urban improvement has not been the subject of a major public information, (55.32 %) of the respondents do not know about the urban improvement project in their neighborhoods; (74.5 %) of respondents have asserted that they are not involved in the project for the improvement. This proves that the inhabitants have not been involved during the preliminary phases and at the one the of project realization.
- The inhabitants show in great majority (85.1 %) the willingness to be involved in the projects, they do not only want to be informed; they are prepared to get more involved (by consultation; Co-design and even partnership).

3. The Operational level

The achievement of urban improvement operations [15]:

- The inexistence of user requirements drawn up by the owner or the prime contractor;
- The unstructured and inconsistency spatial division into zones of the interventions;

- The separation between treatment of space and treatment of social issues
- Paradox: The enterprises chosen for the realization of development works replying administratively to the selection criteria have shown mediocrity in the work execution. Deficiency of the technical monitoring of the realization from the prime contractor or the studies office and the owner or master of the project
- When, during the execution of works of sanitation problems arise or are updated, SEACO's services have very slow reactions and interventions are slow to occur slowing the progress of development works in course; consequence: overshooting deadlines.
- The absence of positive impact of the urban improvement
- The caducity of the actions and operations,
- A very high rate of dissatisfaction, on 100 questioned 93% have expressed dissatisfaction towards the works quality in their neighborhoods, recognizing the problems: for qualification and skills, of incompleteness,
- The absence of the quality in the results of the work of facilities
- The non- appropriation of spaces landscaped
- The non-adhesion of civil society, feeling of discomfort, insecurity and frustration

VII. THE PROJECT FOR THE MODERNIZATION OF CONSTANTINE: MAKE THE STRATEGIC AND OPERATIONAL MANAGEMENT EFFECTIVE!

After this diagnosis, it is clear that the coordination and the management are the key to success of the urban project and operations to urban improvement and even of any other operation. In addition, the acceptability and the complicity from the citizen is realized by a participation beforehand and a continual involvement while considering the inhabitant as a wholly actor in any intervention affecting its space of life.

As well, the recommendations below should allow to a better identifying the constraints and facilitating the implementation of the strategic management and operational management for a better result of the urban project and the operations it encompasses.

A. Create the Function of Assistant to the District to Fill the Role of Urban Mediator and Ensure the Good Management of Proximity:

For process efficiency, four major parameters are to ensure:

- A Device of Pilotage

Ensure the coordination by the contracting authority between the main partners of the project under the impetus of the territorial authority. State services mainly concerned must participate, and other partners can usefully be represented there

- The Participation and Public Information

Initiate consultation with residents and associations in the early studies and throughout the process in order to facilitate understanding of the projects and the implementation of operations.

- The pre-operational studies

Based on the preliminary diagnosis elements, they must help to clarify the operation specific objectives, its quantitative and qualitative content, the means to implement and commitments of each partner. These studies must involve, under the impetus of the local authority; all public and private stakeholders.

- A Device for Monitoring and Evaluation

The evaluation device should be put in place from the start of the operation to allow the steering committee to reorient some actions and modify the convention during the operation if necessary. For this purpose, the main advances but also the brakes or blocking points should be especially studied. Other parameters are also to be considered namely:

B. The Contracting

To meet local management problems contracting, was, in the majority of studied cases, the institutional cooperation mode seen as one aspect of coordination between state and local authorities, the contract was the regulation means promoted by State to meet the challenges of regionalization, complexity and continuity of public action in the territories to upgrade.

C. Creation of a Device (Workshop, Agency, Office) Independent

This device will be in charge of the intervention accompaniment on built spaces, the requalification of public spaces (monitoring, coordination, control, mediation ...) Monitoring is a sine-qua-non for the success. It enables to meet deadlines, reduce skidding or extra costs incurred by poor planning and coordination of interventions (Fig. 6).

Fig. 6 Proposal for reorganization of actors with integration of the workshop of coordination and consultation

D. The Environmental Dimension to Be Taken into Account

It could be achieved by the overall improvement of the environmental quality in accordance with the regulations and ensuring quality.

VIII. CONCLUSION

The management has a primary objective of putting all the competences and all the knowledge in the service of the project whatever it may be. The urban project is complex in its approach and in its process; it has need for tools to reduce this complexity so that it is feasible and operational.

The management of urban project must begin from the strategic management until the management of simple integrated actions in the program of the urban project, namely the operational management. These simple actions and operations affect the success of the project in such a way that the relationship between the strategic and the operational is interactive.

Finally, the linkage between the two strategic dimensions and operational one should be done by a global and continual management that supports the operational realities of the field can forge a workable strategy and flexible while managing the actors who are the key to success of any action. Thus, we can say that the integration of the management is not only necessary for the urban project in general but its integration is essential in any scale including the operational framework to ensure that the approach of the urban project is a success.

REFERENCES

- [1] Avitabile A. «La mise en scène du projet urbain», Ed. l'Harmattan collection villes et entreprises. 325p. 2005.
- [2] J. P. Lacaze, «aménagement sa ville, le choix des maires en matière d'urbanisme», Ed. Le moniteur, Paris, 1988 .
- [3] J.P Lebas, «le management du projet urbain, émergence d'un métier», In horizon point de vue, le moniteur. pp 418.2007.
- [4] Bourdin A. s/d «projet urbain, maîtrise d'ouvrage, commande». Ed. L'Harmattan. 2001.
- [5] Arab N. "La coproduction des opérations urbaines: coopération et conception", In Espaces et sociétés, projet urbain, maîtrise d'ouvrage, commande. Ed. L'Harmattan N° 105/106, pp. 57-81. 2001.
- [6] F. Ascher, «Les nouveaux principes de l'urbanisme», Ed. L'Aube.2001.
- [7] P. Ingallina, «Le projet urbain», Paris, PUF, «Que-sais-je?», 2001.
- [8] J. Rey, «Une nouvelle manière de faire la ville?», Dans Toussaint, J.Y. et Zimmerman, M. (sous la dir. de) Projet urbain, ménager les gens, aménager la ville, Liège, Pierre Mardaga, 1998, p-p 35-48.
- [9] V. Claude, «Le projet urbain, un ici et maintenant ou un nouvel ailleurs? Quelques réflexions sommaire», In Hayot, A & Sauvage, A S/D « le projet urbain. Enjeux, expérimentations et professions » La Villette Paris, 2000, p-p. 61- 77.
- [10] A. Picard, «Euralille, le manager, le maire, l'architecte» Dans Hayot A., Sauvage A. (sous la dir. de), Le projet urbain. Enjeux, expérimentations et professions, La Villette, Paris. 2000, p-p 166-182.
- [11] R. Khelassi, «précision du management». Ed. Houma. Alger, 2011.
- [12] E. Favari, «Reducing complexity in urban infrastructure projects», Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences N° 53, 2012. pp. 9 – 15
- [13] S.E. Cherrad, Al, «Projet de modernisation de la métropole constantinoise PMMC» Wilaya de Constantine, 2007.
- [14] Wilaya de Constantine, Projet de Modernisation, 2011.
- [15] Sassi Boudemagh S s/d «amélioration urbaine et espaces publics, évaluation et perspective» session normal APW, commission aménagement urbain et urbanisme, Avril 2014